

Overview on Clinical and Instrumental Evaluation in Oropharyngeal Dysphagia. Rehabilitation and Treatment

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ABSTRACT

Background: Dysphagia is a frequent and serious complication of different pathologies. It can occur in Neurologic, Oncologic, Traumatologic, demolitive surgery and other pathologies. It can also occur as a complication of radiotherapy or other medical treatments.

Aim: An overview on current and actually used strategies of taking care and taking charge in clinical assessment, instrumental diagnosis and rehabilitation treatments. The description and highlight on oral nutritional skills.

Materials and Methods: Research in indexed library on line about evaluation and treatment of dysphagia and new research published in the last year.

Conclusion: There are traditional and innovative strategies for clinical diagnosis and instrumental evaluation some of those requires perspective randomized trials to demonstrate their efficacy. Improvement in swallowing ability and maintenance of oral nutrition, can be achieved by traditional exercises and speech therapy, using the support of new technological devices. The objective is to reach excellent results in improving the quality of life and maintaining the patient's social and family skills.

Keywords: Dysphagia; Clinical Assessment; Instrumental Evaluation; Rehabilitation

INTRODUCTION

Swallowing is a physiological act consisting of a succession of voluntary neuromuscular events and reflexes which carry food from the mouth into the stomach. It is an action connected and coordinated with other functions such as

breathing and phonation. Two ways in particular are involved in swallowing, the airway channel (breathing) and the digestive tract channel (food transport and all related activities). There is a common trait that sees these two channels join (oropharynx and hypopharynx) and from which dysphagia can develop. In the literature, an organic dysphagia is distinguished, caused by lesions originating between the mouth space and the stomach, and a functional dysphagia, associated with a malfunction of the pharyngeal/esophageal muscles. In adults, the normal swallowing process generally occurs through the phases: Anticipatory Extraoral preparation Buccal stage Oral phase Pharyngeal stage Esophageal and gastric phase The pharyngeal phase in particular is the one that is based on a particularly complex organization of pathways and nerve centers and is a delicate moment as the transit of the bolus is the consequence of three consecutive mechanisms: the lingual thrust, the suction due to the negative pressure created from the hypopharynx and pharyngeal contraction. All this must be coordinated with elevation of the veil and contraction of the pharynx, closure of the airways (upturning of the epiglottis, adduction of the vocal cords) and opening of the oesophageal sphincter. Dysphagia is much more than an impairment of swallowing function; it represents an alteration of the physiological function of transporting liquids and food, from the phase of their preparation, up to the duodenum attributable to alterations of the structures or anatomical functions which must guarantee adequate nutrition and hydration. Since the association between swallowing disorders and the decline in respiratory function is now clear, it is of fundamental importance to carry out targeted instrumental investigations particularly in the earliest stages of the disease to prevent asymptomatic progression up to the appearance of complications on the B.M.I. or respiratory function that occur in advanced clinical stages, when the quality of life is already compromised and the possible treatment options are limited. Dysphagia is often underestimated, due to lack of knowledge of the procedures, and it is not consolidated practice to perform clinical tests or instrumental screening examinations among the population at risk, although specialist evaluations are able to identify all patients at risk of aspiration pneumonia, that is the leading cause of dysphagia-related morbidity and mortality.^[1] The management of the dysphagic patient is complex, it requires a large network of experts, both in the diagnostic and therapeutic phases, made up of specialist doctors and other health professionals, dedicated structures and equipment. It is established that the early taking charge of the patient in multidisciplinary rehabilitation reduces the risk of complications and costs.^[2] The Guidelines for Rehabilitation of the Italian Ministry of Health and the International Consensus (ICON) on assessment of oropharyngeal dysphagia,^[3] state that rehabilitation, care management, education of patients and their care-givers are together crucial to reduce complications, and must be planned within the rehabilitation project by a multidisciplinary team. The need for a team approach to the dysphagic patient is justified by the complexity of the clinical cases, by the heterogenous causes of the disorder, by the involvement of the entire ingestion-digestion tract and the engagement of different medical disciplines with different specialized diagnostic insights. Taking charge by the rehabilitation team guarantees greater effectiveness and a better quality of the interventions with better outcome and economic advantages for the hospitalizations. The aim of the research was to analyze the advantages and limitations, costs and benefits of methods for instrumental diagnosis of swallowing, through a review of the literature and systematic reviews^[4] on the instrumental diagnosis of oropharyngeal dysphagia. The study excluded esophageal dysphagia, which requires different instrumental evaluation techniques and different type of treatments.

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF DIAGNOSTICS

Swallowing Function Clinical Evaluation

In anamnesis are usually used Questionnaires & Swallowing Tests like The Eating Assessment Tool (EAT-10), that is a concise questionnaire that can be applied to screen dysphagia.^[4] It consists of 10 items and each item is scored from 0 (no problem) to 4 (severe problem). A total score of 3 or more is defined as abnormal swallowing function. In a survey of 235 individuals with voice and swallowing disorders, Belafsky et al.^[4] reported the internal consistency to be 0.960 in Cronbach alpha and the test-retest reliability (expressed by intra-class correlation coefficients) to range from 0.72 to 0.91. In 2021, Ozer et al.^[5] investigated 512 patients (aged 60 years and older) in a geriatric outpatient clinic of a tertiary center. They reported that EAT-10 was positively correlated with age, geriatric depression scale, and the timed up-and-go score; but negatively correlated with mini-nutritional assessment-short form, mini-mental state examination, handgrip strength, and hemoglobin values. Dysphagia outcome severity scale (DOSS) and the repetitive saliva swallowing test (RSST) are common means to assess dysphagia. DOSS is a 7-point ordinal scale with a lower score indicating a worse condition.^[6] DOSS had high interrater (90%) and intrarater (93%) agreements, established by four clinicians on 135 patients in a teaching hospital.^[7] RSST examines the ability to voluntarily swallow repeatedly by asking the participant to swallow saliva as many times as possible in 30 sec. Three or more dry swallows within 30 s is considered normal. In a study examining 120 healthy adults and 40 stroke patients in a geriatric sub-acute stroke unit, the sensitivity and specificity of RSST for screening dysphagia were found to be 69% and 93%, respectively.^[8] The most cited dysphagia screening tests in the literature, we can consider, are: Dysphagia Risk Score, that it's a screening test, often used to intercept individuals at risk. This test can be conducted by specialist doctors, speech therapists but also in hospitalized patients by appropriately trained nurses.^[9] The bedside swallowing assessment is useful for a complete assessment of swallowing skills. In our department, anamnesis and screening tests are conducted by nurses and diagnostic tests by doctors and speech therapists. We use a specific folder for the assessment of dysphagia.^[10,11] Gugging Swallowing Screen (GUSS), Standardized Swallowing Assessment (SSA), Toronto Bedside Swallowing Screening Test (TOR-BSST, Acute Stroke Dysphagia Screen (ASDS), Those most applicable by specially trained nurses are: Test Three-oz Water Swallow Test (WST, Smithard Test^[12]) the most used, and its two variants: WST sensitized with pulse oximeter (pathological finding: drop in oxygen saturation greater than 2% after swallowing 10 ml of water) the WST sensitized with auscultation. After having carried out the swallowing test with water, the nurse can also make use of a more in-depth assessment scale - the Bedside Swallow Assessment - which allows to identify patients with swallowing disorders at risk of aspiration through a score. Three-oz Water Swallow test Offer the person, seated and with the head on the axis, 5 ml of still water at room temperature with a spoon 3 times; at each spoonful check that swallowing has taken place, wait a few seconds and if the patient has a severe cough and a gurgling voice, the test is suspended = Grade 4 - Severe dysphagia. If the person does not cough, water is offered directly from the glass, wait a few seconds, the patient is asked to speak to evaluate the quality of the voice: in case of hoarse and/or bubbling voice and cough = Grade 3 - Moderate dysphagia. If only hoarse and/or gurgling voice = Grade 2 - Mild dysphagia. If previously the test is negative, proceed with 50ml of water from the glass. If this is

also negative = Grade 1 – Dysphagia absent. Guss test The Guss test is an internationally validated clinical examination (Gugging Swallowing Screen), consisting of two phases: a first phase of indirect evaluation of the patient's swallowing function subsequently the tests of direct swallowing of substances of first semi-solid consistency, then liquid and finally solid. Based on the score achieved (from 0 to 20, where the maximum score corresponds to a normal diet), the patient is classified into one of 4 categories of dysphagia severity and aspiration risk. Daniels test Daniels' test corresponds to a table where 6 aspiration symptoms are marked: dysphonia dysarthria voluntary cough reduced post-swallowing cough impaired or absent nausea reflex changes in post-swallowing voice. Dysphagia: at least 2 symptoms.^[10,11]

Fiberoptic Endoscopic Evaluation of Swallowing (F.E.E.S.)

Fiberoptic Endoscopic Evaluation of Swallowing (F.E.E.S.) from data obtainable from international literature as well as in our experience, it is evident that remain the gold standard with Videofluorography\scopy (V.F.G.\S.) for the qualitative and quantitative diagnostic evaluation of oropharyngeal dysphagia and the monitoring of the progress achieved with the rehabilitation treatment, together with the functional clinical evaluation.^[13] The advantages of the methods are linked to the better standardization of the procedures and to the possibility of completing the qualitative evaluation with an accurate quantification of the stagnation, the transit of the bolus and the aspiration.^[14] In comparison to V.F.G., the sensitivity of swallowing tests with FEES is 0.88, the specificity is 0.92.6. In particular for FEES there are standardized measurement scales such as the pooling score and the P-SCA score^[15] which allow a classification of dysphagia associated with clinical classification and quantification of aspiration risk based on the amount, location and management of post-swallowing stagnation. These scales also take into account the general conditions of the patient, alertness, age and methods of carrying out the examination.^[15](Figure 1)

Figure 1: FEES: Pond of solid food not perceived.

The advantages of FEES (compared to digital videofluorography) are: No radiation, repeatability of the exam, allows the anatomical view, evaluation of phonation and sensitivity, detection of saliva and pre-examination food stagnation, allows any type of food and long observations, no risk of barium aspiration, low cost, can be performed

at bedside and at home, no radiation. Disadvantages of FEES: does not allow the evaluation of the oral or oesophageal phase, does not allow the quantitative evaluation of the aspirated bolus, poor sensitivity in the evaluation of the overall pharyngolaryngeal motility, invasive examination.^[8] Advantages of videofluorography: It allows to check, process and oral propulsion of the bolus, activation of the reflex, veil, hyoid and larynx elevation, epiglottic collapse, closure of the laryngeal vestibule, opening of the UES, presence/absence of aspiration/penetration, specifying the quality and quantity of inhalation, presence/absence of the cough reflex and its validity, stasis accumulation phenomena, presence/absence of lateral deficits.^[14,16]

Videofluorographic Swallow Study (V.F.G.\S)

Videofluorographic Swallow Study (V.F.G.\S) provides objective information on bolus transport during swallowing (Figure 2). The VFG findings include residue in the valleculae and pyriform sinuses, aspiration [49], and reduced maximal superior and anterior displacement of the hyoid bone and thyroid cartilage during swallowing. Disadvantages of VFG\S: depends on the location and clinical conditions of the patient, quantity and quality of contrast used, method of administration; high dose of radiation absorbed, impossibility of performing it at the patient's bed, interruption of the examination as the bolus in the trachea is highlighted, specific software for digital technique requested, non-standardizable method.^[17] (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Videofluorography: pre and post-swallow aspiration of liquids.

Surface Electromyography (sEMG): Surface Electromyography (sEMG) can be applied to evaluate swallowing muscle activity. The electrodes are put on the skin near the lip over the submental area or suprahyoid region to detect the muscle activity. We can evaluate the activity of the orbicularis oris superior and inferior, masseter, submental muscle groups (anterior belly of the digastric, mylohyoid, and geniohyoid), and the laryngeal strap (infrahyoid and thyrohyoid) muscles. These muscles are selected because they are superficial and involved in the oral and pharyngeal phases of swallowing.^[18] sEMG is able to study some functional aspects of swallowing such as hyper-hypotonia of the pharyngeal wall or cricopharyngeal muscle, but it remains an uncommon technique and with some limitations of use. The advantage of the electromyographic study of the oral propulsive and pharyngeal phase of swallowing is the ability to accurately evaluate and quantify the pathophysiological mechanisms at the basis of

swallowing anomalies and therefore also of oral and pharyngeal dysphagia. It can be performed multiple times on the same patient to evaluate changes and abnormalities found in previous exams. In selected cases, it can offer useful information on the type of rehabilitation treatment and it is crucial to decide whether to infiltrate the upper oesophageal sphincter with botulinum toxin¹⁸. Contraindications to sEMG. Absolute: Infections or inflammations of the neck tissues, "high" tracheostoma at the level of the cricothyroid membrane. Inability to maintain a sitting position. Surgical interventions with deformation of the pharyngolaryngeal structures. Electrostimulators that can interfere with the EMG recording. Related: Severe postural deformations of the neck. Poor cooperation.^[18] (Figure 3)

Figure 3: Electrode placement (A) and signal display (B) for the electromyographic assessment of swallowing muscle activity. Left red vertical line, onset of swallowing; middle red vertical line, peak amplitude; right red vertical line, end of swallowing.

The Submental Longitudinal Ultrasound Technique (SUS)

The submental longitudinal ultrasound technique (SUS), despite the undoubted advantages related to non-invasiveness and the absence of ionizing radiation, is however limited to the evaluation of the trophic conditions of the lingual and swallowing muscles, of the mobility and range of excursion of the bone hyoid bone and the dynamic measurement of the approach between the thyroid cartilage and the hyoid bone during swallowing. Studies on the S.U.S. have been conducted on patients with Parkinson's disease and stroke, but there is still no definitive agreement on the repeatability and reliability of the method compared to normal controls. It can be used for screening, but it is not able to highlight: laryngeal penetration, presence of aspiration, quantity and location of stagnation. Not studied in children, where it may find maximum use.^[19](Figure 4)

Figure 4: Ultrasonographic images show the hyoid movement at the onset of swallowing (A) and the moment of maximal displacement (B). Double-headed line, the distance between the mandible and hyoid bone.

Labeled Bolus Scintigraphy

Labeled bolus scintigraphy is used to evaluate pre-swallowing drop, stagnation, and aspiration and has shown comparable sensitivity and specificity to FEES and VFG, but absorbed radiation dose, lack of dynamic assessment, need for gamma room, make its use limited.^[20]

Maximal Isometric Tongue Pressure (MTP)

Maximal isometric tongue pressure (MTP) is measured by a device with a disposable oral balloon probe and a plastic pipe, such as JMS measurement apparatus (JMS, Hiroshima, Japan) or Iowa Oral Performance Instrument (IOPI).^[21] The balloon is placed in the mouth and the plastic pipe is bitten at the middle of the central incisors with the lips closed. Patients are then asked to raise their tongue and press the balloon to the hard palate for several seconds with the full effort to obtain the maximal tongue pressure.^[22](Figure 5)

Figure 5: Use of Iowa Oral Performance Instrument

Jaw-Opening Force

Jaw-opening force can be employed to measure the strength of the suprahyoid muscles by using the device like jaw-opening force trainer KT2016 (Livet Inc., Tokyo, Japan), a spherometer with a head encircling belt, two belts to secure the mandible to the headencircling belt, a chin cap, and a dynamometer. Participants are asked to open their jaws with their full effort to obtain the value of maximum force.^[23]

Lip Force

Lip Force can be measured by using a device such as Lip de Cum (Cosmo Instruments Co., Ltd., Tokyo, Japan). This instrument records the combinational forces on the vertical axis from sensors implanted into the upper and lower plastic lip holder. The participants are asked to close the lips with the maximal effort to obtain the highest value of lip force. In 2019, Sakai et al. [60] investigated 245 patients admitted for post-acute care and they reported that dysphagia was inversely associated with lip pressure in male and female subjects. The area under curve to discriminate dysphagia was 0.88 (95% CI, 0.81-0.95) for men and 0.84 (95% CI, 0.77-0.90) for women. Furthermore, the cutoff values of lip force for sarcopenic dysphagia were 10.4 Newton for men and 8.5 Newton for women.^[24]

High-Resolution Manometry

High-Resolution Manometry has been employed to assess pharyngeal dysphagia by the measurement of intra-lumen pressure of the gastrointestinal tract.^[25] During swallowing, the upper esophageal sphincter pressure decreases for the passage of the food bolus. Increased upper esophageal sphincter pressure would cause impaired food bolus transit, leading to residue in the pyriform sinuses and post-swallowing aspiration.^[26]

INTERVENTIONS

The interventions to break the vicious circle between dysphagia and malnutrition requires a multi-disciplinary strategy. This include nutrition support, and texture modification of food, swallowing muscle strengthening, physical therapy, speech tratment, I.O.P.I. training, occupational therapy, electrical muscle stimulation, Novafon vibrational therapy, in-exsufflator and E.F.A.tchnology for poor cough; in Cooperation with the patients' families/caregivers is paramount for the treatment success.^[27]

Nutrition Support

Nutrition Support Poor nutritional status is a core characteristic of dysphagia whereas intensive nutrition therapy^[28], combined with muscle strength^[29] is helpful in increasing muscle mass. An integrated protocol for managing patients with sarcopenic dysphagia. The use of personalized diets according to the primary pathology and caloric needs and supplementary nutritional and dihydration supports, are the tools most used by nutritionists after clinical, humoral, strength and impedance measurement evaluation.

Texture Modification of Food

Texture Modification of Food should be incorporated to improve the safety and efficiency of oral eating in patients with sarcopenic dysphagia. In 2016, Carrion et al.^[30] assessed 133 older patients with oropharyngeal dysphagia by using VFSS to explore the association between nutritional status and swallowing. Only 38.2% of the patients with poor nutrition status (defined by Mini-Nutritional Assessment ≤ 23.5) could swallow liquid safely. Thickeners for liquids and modifications of food consistency can be used using homogenizers or blenders to obtain more or less dense or slippery creamy textures or solid diets with different degrees of softness can be evaluated.^[31]

Physical and Occupational Therapy

Physical and Occupational Therapy in addition to swallowing muscle training, intervention for the declined whole-body muscle mass and strength should be given in patients with dysphagia. A combination of exercise and nutritional interventions is essential for the elderly with sarcopenia. Physical therapy emphasizing the strengthening of four limbs brings collateral benefits for swallowing-related muscles.^[32] Passive and active exercises must be performed for the head, neck and trunk district in order to be able to make the most of the rom. articulate to achieve compensation postures. Respiratory exercises are crucial for the correct sequential coupling of the respiratory and swallowing functions and for the implementation of special swallowing manoeuvres. Strengthening exercises of the oral and facial muscles with and without resistance and of the thrust force of the tongue. To enhance masticatory strength, T tubes and other specific oral motor therapy devices can be used. For the recovery of sensitivity, tactile and thermal stimulations must be used inside and outside the oral cavity up to the palatal pillars.^[38]

Swallowing Muscle Strengthening

Swallowing Muscle Strengthening S.M.T. including lingual resistance exercises, breathing training, and tongue exercises can be applied in patients with sarcopenic dysphagia.^[33] Tongue pressure, and width of the upper esophageal sphincter improved after TPRT, (tongue-pressure resistance training). TPRT is the most commonly used strengthening exercise. To perform TPRT, the patient begins to push his/her entire tongue against the palate as hard as possible for 10 s with the mouth closed and then rests for 10 s. In 2017, Kim et al.^[34] suggested performing TPRT five times, two sets per day for a month in subacute stroke survivors with dysphagia.

Vibratory Therapy

Vibratory therapy. Novafon PRO, is a technological tool that delivers vibratory energy in order to stimulate both masticatory and swallowing muscle reinforcement also through special intraoral stimulation heads. The vibratory energy can be adjusted to 2 frequencies 50Hz and 100Hz and 3 different levels of intensity, in relation to the muscles to be treated and the identified treatment protocols. Therapeutic Action Of Novafon Pro. Regulation Of Muscle Tone: In treatment with NovafonPRO device, the vibrations reach a depth of six centimeters in the tissue. When vibrations encounter a muscle, muscle tone balances out and normalizes, as a result the muscle's potential for strength increases³⁵. This reflex is also known as the tonic vibration reflex. Pain Relief: Local Vibration Therapy has the function of relieving pain. The so-called "Gate Control" theory claims that pain stimuli can be overwhelmed by

other factors such as vibration, heat and pressure. The transmission of pain in the nervous system is interrupted.. Stimulation Of Blood And Lymphatic Circulation: in order of the muscular contractions generated by the vibrations, improve blood and lymphatic circulation. The local regulation mechanisms of the tissues and vessels will be strengthened and there will be an acceleration of the regeneration and repair mechanisms in the tissue. Sensitivity Stimulation: The brain is in constant contact with the peripheral nervous system. This means that skin, muscles, joints and tendons are constantly sending information about location, touch, pain and temperature. Damage to the nerves at certain points can lead to sensitivity problems, which manifest themselves, for example, in loss of receptivity, numbness, etc. Local vibration therapy helps to stimulate the exchange of information through the stimulation of the affected tissue, improving superficial and internal sensitivity. Therapy Objectives of Local Vibration Therapy In the rehabilitation of neurological diseases, is the treatment of spasticity, sensitivity or sensorimotor disorders. The goal is to maintain or regain function and make daily activities easier³⁶.

Electrostimulation of the Swallowing Muscles

Electrostimulation of the swallowing muscles with different protocols and paradigms of treatment and electrode placement. The therapy is performed using surface electrodes and dedicated devices (Vital Stim - Ami-Pro2), it is a valid support in the path of recovery of muscle strength, especially in uncooperative patients³⁷. The safety of the treatment with electrostimulation in patients with neoplastic pathology, or with pacemakers has not been verified.

Botulinum Toxin

Botulinum Toxin finds particular indications in case of hypertonicity of the upper esophageal sphincter, through ultrasound-guided or EMG-guided infiltration.

Alternative Strategies of Nutrition and Hydration

When it is not possible to maintain oral nutrition, an alternative nutrition way must be chosen, to prevent sarcopenia and malnutrition, preferably by exploiting the enteric tube via PEG or SNG or alternatively by exploiting parenteral nutrition.

In Patients with Tracheostomy

In patients with tracheostomy, the cannula will be capsized as soon as possible to allow laryngeal elevation, and when possible the cannula will be removed to allow the supra- and subglottic pressure differences to be restored.

In-Exsufflator and E.F.A. Technology

Ab ingestis” pneumonia is the second most common cause of nosocomial infections in inpatients and the most common cause of death in patients with dysphagia. Rates increase dramatically in patients with neurological diseases or an acquired brain injury. Early interdisciplinary rehabilitation protocols could reduce penetration-aspiration episodes. The effects of an expiratory flow accelerator (EFA®) device - usually aimed to manage airway

secretions - in addition to usual care and in-exsufflator is able to prevent the penetration-aspiration (PA) risk in bedridden dysphagic low-alert patients, with ineffective cough, compared to a “usual care” control group 1,2.

DISCUSSION

The rehabilitation treatment plan and program is drafted by the dysphagia rehabilitation team with the family and caregiver. After the first functional and instrumental evaluation, the team proceeds by objectives with pre-set times, verification of the results and reformulation of the project. Periodic meetings of the team with the family are planned. In the initial stages of the disease, and after an accurate diagnosis, it is possible to recover the functions of mastication and swallowing, returning to functional normality. In advanced stages, or in chronic/progressive degenerative diseases, it can be considered a success, being able to maintain basic and vital skills even with aids, for a perceived satisfactory quality of life. For the recovery and maintenance of nutritional and swallowing skills in safety and autonomy, an intensive multidisciplinary rehabilitation treatment will be required by a medical, speech-language pathologist, neuromotor, occupational, specialized team, to obtain the stabilization of the basic skills for maintaining of autonomy in ADLs; the recovery of the neuromotor control of the head/neck area, of the postural stability of the trunk³⁹. Clinical and instrumental physiatric medical screening has made it possible to identify subjects at risk of bronchial and pulmonary infections whose symptoms, although present, have never been investigated in depth. It is of fundamental importance to provide the right indications to all patients on the strategies necessary to compensate for the swallowing deficit, on the interventions of alternative feeding strategies, on the different possibilities of modifying the textures of foods. It is important to acquire correct postural strategies and attitudes to adopt during the meal, the compensation postures of the head, the oral hygiene interventions, the exercises proposed by the speech therapists, both for patients, family members and their care-givers, to become aware of the dimension of the problem sometimes not identified, but often underestimated or denied. The contribution of new technologies in the treatment with the use of specific devices integrates and reinforces the effectiveness of the treatment particularly in uncooperative patients or with alterations in the state of consciousness.

CONCLUSIONS

Screening, clinical and instrumental evaluation of oropharyngeal dysphagia demonstrate great validity and effectiveness both in the diagnosis and evaluation of the pathology, and in planning the rehabilitation treatment. Avoiding dangerous nutritional or hydration deficiencies, and episodes of laryngeal aspiration and consequent aspiration pneumonia, represents a primary objective for the survival, autonomy and quality of life of dysphagic patients. It is also crucial to significantly reduce the costs of assistance and the increase in the number of days of hospitalization due to dehydration, malnutrition and episodes of pneumonia. The standardization of non-invasive screening methods must make available a broader toolkit for choosing the most appropriate rehabilitation program. Further scientific studies with adequate protocol design are needed to validate new promising diagnostic and therapeutic procedures.

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